

The Effect of Biochar and Nitrogen Doses on Yield and Mineral Concentrations in Peanut

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Abstract

In this study, effect of biochar and nitrogen doses on the yield of peanut plants and the nutrient element contents of leaves were investigated. For this purpose, 2 tons da⁻¹ biochar and biochar + nitrogen applications were grown during the vegetation period. The fruit weights of the harvested plants and the N, P, K, Ca, Mg, Fe, Zn, Cu, Mn, and B concentrations of peanut leaves were determined. As a result of the research, the highest fruit weight nitrogen and the highest N concentration were determined in the biochar + 10 kg da⁻¹ N application. According to the results, there was a 5% decrease in fertilizer requirement as a result of the application of biochar to the soil in peanut plants. The effect of the applications increased the Ca, Mn, and Cu concentrations while decreasing the P, K, Mg Fe, Zn concentrations. The effects of the applications on B concentrations were different. As a result of this research, it is possible to say that mixing biochar and nitrogen will be an effective method for more effective use.

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1. Introduction

Peanut (*Arachis hypogaea* L.) is one of the most critical oil crops and food legumes in the world and is grown in many arid and semiarid regions. Peanut differs from other plants in that it produces its fruits underground. Peanut is a valuable plant that contains 45-60% oil, 20-30% protein, 18% carbohydrates, vitamins, and minerals in its seeds and is used in various ways, especially in the oil industry and snack making, and its stems are used as dry grass. Peanut seeds are quite rich in terms of protein content. The fact that the amino acids that make up the protein in peanuts are easily digestible increases their nutritional value (Doğan, 2007). Soil water deficiency and nutrient deficiency are the two main factors that limit the growth, development, and yield of peanuts in arid and semiarid regions. Nitrogen is a macro element for crop growth and is generally deficient in arid soils (Lindquist et al., 2010). The yield has been increased with chemical fertilizers applied for years in peanut farming, but these applications have caused soil fatigue and even barrenness and decreased soil vitality after many years. To prevent this situation, organic fertilizers have been used in agriculture. The increasing world population and the changing nutritional and food requirements that develop accordingly have brought a new perspective to agricultural inputs and applied methods. In the developing global world, technology has been used intensively to obtain more products from a unit area. For this reason, more pesticides have been used to minimize product loss, more chemical fertilizers have been used to increase product quality and quantity, and much more water has been used to increase the uptake of the fertilizers used by the plants. Thus, excessive use of inputs has started to have many negative effects on the environment. The use of the main material of the soil, which has an important place in agricultural activities, is an indispensable necessity to ensure its function and continuity of production. The way to achieve this is to use the soil as much as possible for its purpose and without damaging it. Studies should be carried out to investigate alternative cultivation possibilities that provide

less chemical fertilizer use. In addition to the negative effects of excessive nitrogenous fertilizer use on soil flora, especially in developed countries, its storage in various plants, the decrease in plant resistance to diseases and pests, and its mixing with groundwater and drinking water cause significant problems in terms of human health and economy. The fact that nitrous acid, which occurs due to excessive nitrogenous fertilizer use, is defined as one of the factors causing the depletion of the ozone layer in the atmosphere, indicates the importance of the issue and is thought-provoking in terms of revealing the extent to which the danger may reach in the future. Various researchers stated that the effects of developments in agriculture and industry on the natural nitrogen balance are in the form of NO_3^- accumulation in waters and some soils and nitrous oxide (NO_2) accumulation in the atmosphere (Coşkan et al., 2007; Doğan et al., 2006; Coşkan, 2004). In Turkey, a large part of the waste that causes environmental pollution and remains after agricultural production is directly burned or left in the field. There is a wrong approach to dispose of these wastes, which are very valuable in terms of agriculture. If these residues or wastes released as a result of agricultural activities are stored in an uncontrolled manner or applied to soils, the expected benefits from the residues or wastes cannot be provided. Turkey's annual biomass potential was estimated at 109.4 million tons (FAO, 2022). Biochar is obtained by the thermochemical change of various plant and animal wastes under high temperature and minimum oxygen conditions. The obtained material has the potential to eliminate the deficiency of organic matter thanks to its properties such as high carbon content, large surface area and resistance to decomposition. Due to its positive properties compared to organic matter, studies on biochar have increased in recent years (Luo and Gu, 2016). Biochar is a term that emerged about soil management and carbon (C) enrichment. Biochar is a carbon-rich product obtained by pyrolysis of biomass such as wood, straw, leaves and animal residues in a closed

environment with little or no oxygen (Lehmann et al., 2006). Biochar has been proposed as a useful agricultural management tool to improve soil quality and product productivity and to minimize environmental problems caused by inadequate waste disposal (Haider et al., 2017; Haider et al., 2020). Studies conducted by some researchers showed that there is an important biochar-nitrogen fertilizer interaction, where higher yields were observed with increasing biochar application rates in the presence of N fertilizer and basic fertilization (Chan et al., 2007; Zwieten et al., 2010; Jeffery et al., 2011; Kemer, 2018).

This study aims to examine the effects of nitrogen applications with biochar application on determining the appropriate fertilizer dose in peanuts, the content of plant nutrients in the leaves of biochar, and the yield of peanut fruits.

2. Material and Methods

Soil samples were taken from a 0-30 cm depth as reported by Jackson (1958) from the experimental area of Çine District of Aydın Province (Table 1). After the soil sample was air-dried in the laboratory and passed through a 2 mm sieve, pH was determined according to Jackson (1958), electrical conductivity (EC) by Richards (1954), organic matter (OM) by Jackson (1958), lime by Hızalan and Ünal (1966), total N by Bremner (1965), available P by Olsen et al. (1954), available K, Na, Ca and Mg by Pratt (1965) and available Fe, Zn, Cu and Mn by Lindsay and Norvell (1978). When the study soils in terms of available plant nutrients before planting is examined, it was seen that they were at sufficient levels in terms of nutrients other than phosphorus (Table 1). The research area soils were loamy, salt-free, calcareous, and insufficient in terms of organic matter before the trial. Biochar was obtained from Oak (*Quercus coccifera* L.) pruning waste. Dry oak pruning waste was

manually crushed to 10-15 cm, and its dimensions were reduced. Biochar was performed in the Updraft Gasifier Supported – Fixed Bed Pyrolysis System. This system has a waste processing capacity of 25 kg hour⁻¹. Biochar production was carried out at 450-550°C for approximately one hour. The pyrolysis temperature was measured with K-type thermocouples. The yield of biochar obtained from dry oak pruning waste is 27% based on mass. The biochar pH was 7.77. Biochar was applied at 2 tons da⁻¹. In the experiment, urea (46% N) was used as a nitrogen source, and applications were made at 5 kg da⁻¹ and 10 kg da⁻¹. P₂O₅ was applied to each subject with DAP fertilizer (18-46%) as 3 kg da⁻¹ together with planting. Applications were: Control ((A₁), 2 tons da⁻¹ biochar (A₂), 5 kg da⁻¹ N (A₃), 10 kg da⁻¹ N (A₄), 5 kg da⁻¹ N + 2 tons da⁻¹ biochar (A₅) and 10 kg da⁻¹ N + 2 tons da⁻¹ biochar (A₆). The trial plot sizes were 2m x 5m, and each block consisted of 3 plots. All of the biochar, phosphorus and nitrogen were applied to the trial area together with planting and mixed into the soil. The peanut was sown manually in April 2022, and the harvest was made manually in August. After harvest, the plants were washed first with tap water and then with distilled water and dried in an air drying cabinet at 65 °C until they reached a constant weight. The dried plants were ground. In these samples, N, P, K, Ca, Mg, Fe, Zn, Cu, Mn, and B analyses were performed. The N content of the leaf samples was determined by using the modified Kjeldahl method; P, K, Ca, Mg, Fe, Mn, Zn and Cu nitric-perchloric acid mixture and wet-digesting the filtrate using ICP-OES (Kacar and İnal 2008). Fruit yield was determined based on 10 plants randomly harvested by hand from each plot row, and the fruits were cleaned after being separated from the plants. Then, they were weighed, and the weight of fruits from an average root was noted.

Table 1. Some chemical properties of the soil at the depth of 0-30 cm

Parameters	Values	Parameters	Values
pH	7.81	Ca (mg kg ⁻¹)	6123
EC (dS m ⁻¹)	0.49	Mg (mg kg ⁻¹)	411
CaCO ₃ (%)	3.5	Fe (mg kg ⁻¹)	8
OM (%)	1.68	Mn (mg kg ⁻¹)	6
P (mg kg ⁻¹)	4.33	Cu (mg kg ⁻¹)	2
K (mg kg ⁻¹)	289	Zn (mg kg ⁻¹)	2.2

2.1. Statistical analysis

The experiment was designed according to the randomized block design. There are three replications for each application. Analysis of variance (ANOVA) test was performed for the data using JMP software (JMP 8.0). Differences between applications were compared using the LSD test. The results were expressed in letter form next to the means.

3. Results and Discussion

The effects of biochar and nitrogen applications on fruit weight were found to be

statistically significant (Table 2). The lowest fruit weight was found in the control (115 g) and only biochar application (117 g). The highest fruit yield was obtained from 10 kg da⁻¹ N +2 tons da⁻¹ biochar application (A₆). Furthermore, higher fruit yield was obtained in A₄ application (10 kg da⁻¹ N) than in A₅ application (5 kg da⁻¹ N +2 tons da⁻¹ biochar). 10 kg da⁻¹ N application with and without biochar was found to be higher in terms of yield than the 5 kg da⁻¹ N application.

Table 2. Effect of applications on fruit weight

Applications	Fruit weight (g root ⁻¹)
A ₁	115e**
A ₂	117e
A ₃	146d
A ₄	247b
A ₅	156c
A ₆	261a

**p≤0.01, letters indicate differences between applications.

Lehmann et al. (2003) and Gul et al. (2015) explained the effect of biochar applications on productivity by reducing the leaching of nutrients applied with fertilizers and increasing fertilizer use efficiency due to the high water and nutrient retention ability of biochar. Esposito (2013) stated that the application of biochar to the soil significantly increased plant growth in wheat plants compared to the control. Zhang et al. (2016) investigated the effects of biochar applied with balanced fertilization and high fertilization on corn plant yield compared to soils where only fertilization was applied. In the study, it was observed that corn plant yield increased, especially with balanced fertilization and biochar application. Şenay (2022) showed that the effect of biochar applications on wheat was different, and the highest yield was determined in the 2 tons da⁻¹

application. The effects of the applications on leaf N, P, and K concentrations are given in Table 3. It was determined that the effect of the application doses on N contents of peanut plants was statistically significant. The highest N content was obtained from (A₆) 10 kg/daN +2 tons/da biochar application (4.1%). The lowest N content was obtained from the control application with 3.1%. When the N applications without biochar were compared (A₃ and A₄), 3% increases were determined in the A₅ application and 5% in the A₆ application. According to the study conducted by Jeffery et al. (2011), they stated that there was a 10% decrease in nitrogenous fertilizer requirement as a result of the application of biochar to the soil. Similarly, an increase was recorded in the N element in a study conducted on wheat (Şenay, 2022). Previous studies

showed that biochar applications result in increased N availability and retention when applied together with N fertilizers (Chan et al., 2007; Steiner et al., 2008; Van Zwieten et al., 2010). Researchers confirmed that biochar can effectively increase nutrient availability by retaining ammonium ions in the soil and inhibiting the nitrification of nitrogen as a soil amendment (Spokas et al., 2009). When the peanut leaf P contents of the applications were evaluated, it was seen that the highest value was in the A₁ application (0.24%), and this value decreased with biochar and nitrogen doses. It was determined that leaf K contents decreased with biochar and increased nitrogen

fertilizer application compared to the control application (2.51%) as in potassium and phosphorus. The lowest K contents were obtained from A₅ and A₆ (1.57%). In previous studies conducted with biochar, it was concluded that post-harvest soil pH increased (Rondon et al., 2007; Yamato et al., 2006; Majeed et al., 2018). The reason for the decrease in P may be due to the increase in soil pH. Manolikaki and Diamadopoulos (2017) found that biochar applications decreased phosphorus in alkaline loam soil. They also observed no yield gains if biochar applications were not supplemented with inorganic fertilization, except for P.

Table 3. Effect of applications on leaf N, P, K concentrations (%)

Applications	N	P	K
A ₁	3.1E**	0.24A*	2.51A**
A ₂	3.3D	0.23AB	2.00B
A ₃	3.7C	0.21AB	1.82BC
A ₄	3.9B	0.22ABC	1.86B
A ₅	3.8BC	0.20C	1.57C
A ₆	4.1A	0.20C	1.57C

**p<0.01, *p<0.05, letters indicate differences between applications.

The effects of biochar and nitrogen applications on leaf Ca and Mg concentrations are given in Table 4. The effects of the applications on peanut leaf calcium and magnesium contents were statistically significant. While the lowest Ca content was obtained from the control application (1.46%), 1.61% Ca content was obtained in the application with only biochar. A₅ and A₆ applications contained 2.03% and 1.86% Ca, respectively, and an increase in leaf Ca contents was determined with increasing nitrogen and biochar doses. Similarly, an increase was recorded in a study conducted on wheat (Şenay, 2022) and in another study conducted on corn (Majeed et al. 2018) and in rye (Manolikaki and Diamadopoulos 2017). The effect of biochar and nitrogen applications

on Mg concentration in plant leaves was found to be statistically significant. Magnesium values were determined in the range of 0.68-1.00% and did not increase with application doses. Mg, which was 0.86% in the control application, increased to 1.00% in the A₂ application. It decreased to 0.75% in the A₆ application. In the study conducted by Uzoma et al. (2011), they investigated the effects of biochar obtained from farmyard manure (0, 10, 15 and 20 t ha⁻¹) on the development of corn plants and reported that there were decreases in Mg concentration of corn plants with biochar application. Furthermore a decrease in corn Mg content (Nelson et al. 2011) and Inal et al. (2015) reported that Mg concentrations in corn plants decreased in calcareous soils.

Table 4. Effect of applications on leaf Ca and Mg concentrations (%)

Applications	Ca	Mg
A ₁	1.46D**	0.86AB*
A ₂	1.61CD	1.00A
A ₃	1.79BC	0.72C
A ₄	1.71BC	0.68C
A ₅	2.03A	0.88AB
A ₆	1.86AB	0.75BC

**p<0.01, *p<0.05, letters indicate differences between applications.

The effects of biochar and nitrogen applications on leaf Fe and Zn concentrations are given in Table 5. Applications at different levels had statistically different effects on the Fe content of plant leaves. While Fe concentrations had the highest value of 226 mg kg⁻¹ in the control application, they had the lowest value of 65 mg kg⁻¹ in the A₄ application. A decrease in Fe concentration was observed with the applications compared to the control application. Biochar and nitrogen doses had a statistical effect on plant leaf Zn values. Zinc concentration were determined in the range of 25-31 mg kg⁻¹. When biochar and nitrogen application doses were compared, the highest Zn concentration was determined as 33 mg kg⁻¹ in the A₃ application and the lowest

value was determined as 25 mg kg⁻¹ in the A₂ and A₆ applications. The decrease in Fe and Zn contents was found in previous studies that biochar increases soil pH (Rondon et al., 2007; Yamato et al., 2006; Majeed et al., 2018). It can be said that plant Fe and Zn contents may have decreased with increasing pH. Majeed et al., (2018) conducted a greenhouse study to determine the effect of three different biochars (Pine, Poplar and Oak biochar), four different biochar doses (0, 1, 2 and 4%) and four different nitrogen applications (0, 70, 140 and 210 mg kg⁻¹) on nutrient uptake by corn plants. As a result of the biochar application, they stated that the nutrient element contents of different biochars such as Fe, Zn and Mn were different.

Table 6. Effect of applications on leaf Fe, Zn concentrations (mg kg⁻¹)

Applications	Fe	Zn
A ₁	226A**	31AB*
A ₂	187B	25D
A ₃	89CD	33A
A ₄	65D	29BC
A ₅	93C	26CD
A ₆	67CD	25D

**p<0.01, *p<0.05, letters indicate differences between applications.

The effects of biochar and nitrogen applications on leaf Mn, Cu, B concentrations are given in Table 6. Biochar and nitrogen doses had a statistically significant effect on Mn concentration in the plant leaves. Manganese concentration was determined in the range of 30-91 mg kg⁻¹ and increased with application doses. Compared to the control application, Mn concentration, which was 30 mg kg⁻¹, increased to 91 mg kg⁻¹ in the A₅ application. Increasing the biochar dose increased the concentrations of Mn in the corn leaves (Majeed et al., 2018). Inal et al. (2015) reported that Mn concentrations increased in

bean plants in calcareous soils. The effect of biochar and nitrogen application doses on Cu concentration of peanut plant leaves showed a statistically significant difference with the applied doses and was found to be significant. According to biochar and nitrogen application doses, Cu concentration was determined in the range of 6.4-9.2 mg kg⁻¹. As a general result of the applications, it was observed that Cu content was the lowest in A₁ application and the highest in A₃, A₄ and A₅ applications. The statistical effect of biochar and nitrogen doses on plant leaf B concentration was found to be significant. B concentration were determined

as 41 mg kg⁻¹ in the control application, 45 mg kg⁻¹ in the A₂ application, 43 mg kg⁻¹ in the A₃ application, 37 mg kg⁻¹ in the A₄ application,

44 mg kg⁻¹ in the A₅ application and 36 mg kg⁻¹ in the A₆ application.

Table 7. Effect of applications on leaf Mn, Cu, B concentrations (mg kg⁻¹)

Applications	Mn	Cu	B
A ₁	30E**	6.4C*	41BC*
A ₂	32E	7.8B	45A
A ₃	77B	9.2A	43AB
A ₄	60D	9.2A	37CD
A ₅	91A	9.2A	44AB
A ₆	71CD	9.0A	36D

**p≤0.01, *p≤0.05, letters indicate differences between applications.

4. Conclusion

The effects of biochar applications on biomass varied; the highest fruit weight amounts were determined in the 10 kg da⁻¹ N + 2 tons da⁻¹ biochar application. While no significant effect was observed with nitrogen-free biochar, the greatest fruit weight increase was observed with the application of biochar plus N fertilizers. In this study, biochar applications caused increases in yield together with N fertilizer. When evaluated especially according to the soil and plant characteristics used in the experiment, it was concluded that 2 tons da⁻¹ application can be recommended as the biochar application dose. The evaluation of agricultural wastes with biochar may contribute to our country's economy and will contribute to reducing environmental pollution. More studies are needed to understand the reactions of plants and soil to biochar and to develop recommendations for specific biochars in different soils.

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